

ANALYSIS THE VARIOUS CONSTRAINTS FACED BY ENROLLED FEMALE STUDENTS IN GETTING HIGHER EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

The current study was aimed to analyze the *Various Constraints faced by enrolled female students in getting higher education*. For this purpose, the data was collected through a well-designed questionnaire using multistage stratified random sampling and selected 127 respondents from Wari Campus of Shaheed BB University. The collected data were analyzed through SPSS. The results show that, co-education is disrespected in Pakhtoon Society, lack of transportation facilities and women harassment is a hurdle to female higher education. Furthermore, gender discrimination, poverty, people think that female higher education dishonors their family, shortage of educational institution, early marriages of females, lack of hostel facility, preference to male higher education as compared to female higher education and long distance to educational institutions are various associated factors for low female higher education. The present research recommends that the both the government and non-government organizations should focus on creating awareness regarding the importance of female higher education by providing educational facilities (i.e. scholarships) as well as provide more employment opportunities and technical skills to enhance female higher education.

Keywords:

INTRODUCTION

Education is the process of training man as a member of society to achieve his goals by using all his abilities to the maximum. Education is every interaction that happens, every connection that happens between an adult and a child. Education means bringing out the generally valid ideas latent in the minds of every individual (Allen, 1988). Higher education covers a more extensive scope of higher level learning establishments including the college and Universities. These higher learning establishments could be coordinated in various

ways (AssiéLumumba, 2005). Higher education develops women's participation and inclusion in the development process and gives them the chances and opportunities to increase their self-confidence and self-esteem. It also increases one's capacity for critical thought. Higher education runs into the social position of women that is predominate in society, where women mainly stay inside their houses and simply help out with housework. These societal taboos are discouraged and reduced by higher education, which also gives

women new roles and opportunities (Saira Zafar Khan, 2015). The traditional Pashtuns live in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, the northernmost province of Pakistan, which encompasses the tribal regions of North Waziristan, South Waziristan, Malakand, Mohmand, Kurram, and Orakzai. According to a 2012 UNESCO assessment, about 80% of the women in this Northern Province are denied access to higher education. This is deplorable predicament that the women in this region find themselves in, including familial, economic, and tribal Pakhtun cultural factors. The socio-cultural structure of this region, however, is the main cause of this dreadful state of female's higher education. The elements include male chauvinism, underage marriages, and disapproval of working women in society, sexual assaults, and the right of men to make decisions (UNESCO, 2012).

Objectives of the study

- (1) To find out about the interest of female in higher education.
- (2) To know about the reasons responsible for women deprivation from getting higher education.
- (3) To put forward recommendations for women higher education.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Higher education gives women a boost in terms of confidence, prestige, and honour in society. It also reduces their financial dependence, increases their role in society, expands their opportunities, and aids in the healthier upbringing of their offsprings (Sharma & Afroz, 2014). In their discussion of the social roles and involvement of women in society, Benish, Auraj, Nadeem, Bhatti, and Nawaz came to the conclusion that the ability of women to make decisions is closely correlated with their level of education. The level of awareness and engagement of educated women in society's decision-making is favourable, and their education strengthens their position by fostering and supporting gender equality in society (Nawaz et al., 2017). In Pakistan women employment is rare. The ratio of women employment is different in rural and urban areas. In rural areas restrictions on women work more often than in urban regions, but typically aren't allowed to work since families view it as dishonourable and shameful (Malik & Aamir, 2017). Pakistan continues to be near the bottom of the list for the percentage of women in

the labour force, which are fewer than the global average of 51%. (Sarwar & Abbasi, 2013). According to a survey by the Global Gender Gap Index, Pakistan continues to rank 148 out of 149 nations in terms of gender equality, which demonstrates the country's declining and deteriorating situation in this area. (Ahmed, 2018). Mukhtar and Rashid have discussed a variety of problems affecting women's access to education, including infrastructure issues, the underrepresentation of women in the field of education, the government's lack of interest in supporting educational advancement, high school dropout rates, etc (Rashid & Mukhtar, 2012). Lack of funding for the education sector is another major obstacle faced by women in the field of education. The problems that women face are greater than the funds allocated for women's education ('Lack of Funds a Hurdle to Women's Empowerment' | Pakistan Today, 2012).

Women are denied form educational and health facilities. Social taboos do not allow women to have access to a decent job or employment. Uneducated women are more prone to violence and abuses, mostly families also deprive their daughters from property rights (Choudhry, et al., 2019b). According to a report of Oslo Summit on Education resource distribution in education sector of Pakistan is of a serious concern. The federal government should increase the educational resources of least developed provinces, and the distribution of resources within the provinces is also necessary (Dr. Rabea Malik, 2015). Higher education can help to improve female emancipation. Women benefit from higher education in two ways. It enables capable women to assume positions of leadership in society and to serve as role models for younger girls. Additionally, it aids women in selecting areas of expertise, whether this is as decision-makers by influencing social, economic and cultural policy concerns or by their involvement in family and community life (Shaukat & Siddiquah, 2013).

Compared to uneducated women, educated women feel more in charge of their life and have more authority and influence over the family's resources. As a result of their increased social standing, they are better able to understand and recognise the negative aspects of their current situation. The educated woman can see a better future and the likelihood of achieving it. She can see what is doable and what she needs to do to

make a difference (Usha & Sharma, 2001). Educated women have more authority and autonomy while also elevating their prestige. They can benefit from this empowerment both within the family and household and at the community, regional, and national levels (Friedmann, 1992; Zafar, 2004). In Pakistan a growing number of girls are pursuing higher education despite cultural obstacles. This reflects a change in society and is

mostly an urban phenomenon. In certain instances, at the higher educational level, girls even outnumber boys. Given that a sizable fraction of the population is participating in academic activities, this tendency appears to be beneficial for the growth of Pakistani Society (Maqsood et al., 2012).

RESEACH METHODOLOGY

Proportional allocation of sample size in various departments of Shaheed BB University Wari Campus- (Study area.)

S.No	Name of department	Program	Semester within each department	Number of total female enrolled in each department	Sample size of total female students in each department
01	Social Work	BS	2 nd semester	07	05
			4 th semester	02	01
			6 th semester	01	01
			8 th semester	04	03
02	Education	BS	2 nd semester	12	08
			4 th semester	05	03
			6 th semester	16	11
			8 th semester	05	03
03	Environmental Science	BS	2 nd semester	03	02
			4 th semester	02	01
			6 th semester	01	01
			8 th semester	01	01
04	Zoology	BS	2 nd semester	25	17
			4 th semester	14	09
			6 th semester	30	20
			8 th semester	15	10
05	Botany	BS	2 nd semester	10	08
			4 th semester	08	05
			6 th semester	11	07
			8 th semester	16	11
06	Physical Education	BS	2 nd semester	0	
			4 th semester	0	
			6 th semester	0	
			8 th semester	0	
Total				188	127

METHODS AND MATERIALS

Universe of the research study

Universe of the research was the sub Campus Wari of Shaheed BB University. Data was collected from the female students enrolled in BS program at the campus. To get the authentic information the study area is further divided, into

different departments like, Social Work, Education , Physical education , Botany, Zoology and Environmental science.

Sampling procedure

Sample is a Part which represents the whole target population's qualities and characteristics while the procedure through which we collect the

samples from selected population is called sampling process, multistage stratified random sampling methods was used. Selected Wari Campus of Shaheed BB University first. All six (6) departments then selected for research study. After this process, female students were focused in each and every department of the universe, the respondents in each department were picked through random sampling method, it is a method, where each element in the population had equal and independent chance per selection.

Sample size:

Proportional allocation method was used to determine the sample size from each selected department. A sample size of 127 respondents had been finally determined on the bases of procedure designed by Sekaran (2003) table 03 shows detail.

Tools for data collection

Interview schedule was used for data collection, with face to face interview method as a procedure. The interview schedule was designed on the basis of objectives.

Data analysis:

SPSS software was used for the data analysis, including percentage proportion with frequency distributive of the same.

Data analysis

SPSS software was used for data analysis and got percentage and frequency distribution.

Perception of the respondents about female higher education

S.NO	Statements	Yes	No	Total
01	Female higher education is the way to women empowerment.	127 100%	0 0%	127 (100%)
02	You have conducive environment for getting higher education.	125 (98.4)	5 (1.6)	127 (100%)
03	Females have barriers in getting higher education.	118 (92.8%)	9 (7.2%)	127 (100%)
04	Female higher education is liked/accepted in our society.	86 (67.1%)	41 (32.9%)	127 (100%)
05	Co-education is still disrespected in Puchtoon society.	69 (54.4%)	58 (45.6%)	127 (100%)
06	Female access to higher education is less due to transportation facilities.	97 (76.9%)	30 (23.1%)	127 (100%)
07	Women harassment is a hurdle to female higher education.	111 (87.1%)	16 (12.9%)	127 (100%)
08	Due to gender discrimination people just educate male members in their family.	90 (70.3%)	37 (29.7%)	127 (100%)
09	Poverty is responsible for less female access to higher education.	92 (72.9%)	35 (27.1%)	127 (100%)
10	People think that female higher education dishonors their family.	109 (85.5%)	18 (14.5%)	127 (100%)
11	Shortage of educational institutions is responsible for female no access to higher education.	107 (84.9%)	20 (15.1%)	127 (100%)
12	Earlier marriage of females is also a problem in the way of female higher education.	109 (85.5)	18 (14.5%)	127 (100%)
13	Lack of boarding facility is a major problem in the way of female higher education.	78 (61.6%)	49 (38.4%)	127 (100%)
14	Less number of female students does not encourage rest of the female students	89 (70.5%)	38 (29.5%)	127 (100%)
15	Your parents favor women higher education.	112 (88.8%)	15 (11.2%)	127 (100%)
16	Your family prefers male higher education as compared to female higher education.	80 (62.3%)	47 (37.7%)	127 (100%)

17	Most of parents do not send their daughters to higher education institutions due to long distance	110 (86.3%)	17 (13.7%)	127 (100%)
18	You like female higher education	109 (85.5%)	18 (14.5%)	127 (100%)
19	Our culture is male dominant which has a very less space for female higher education.	101 (79.1%)	26 (20.9%)	127 (100%)
20	The environment inside the education institute is conducive for female education.	95 (74.3%)	32 (25.7%)	127 (100%)
21	Separate educational institutions will encourage female higher education.	115 (90.4%)	12 (9.6%)	127 (100%)
22	You face hurdles in getting higher education.	114 (89.6%)	13 (10.4%)	127 (100%)
23	You encourage your relatives for female higher education in your locality.	93 (73.7%)	34 (26.3%)	127 (100%)

The above mentioned table elaborated the response of the respondents about the Female Higher Education, among that 127(100%) of the respondents, 127 (100%) were agree with the statement that Female higher education is the way to women empowerment and 0 (0%) were not agree with this statement. 125 (98.4) of the respondents were agree with the statement that You have conducive environment for getting higher education and 5 (1.6%) were not agree with the statement. 118 (92.8%) were agree with the statement that Females have barriers in getting higher education and 9 (7.2%) were not agree with the statement. 86 ((67.1%) were agree with the statement that Female higher education is liked/accepted in our society and 41 (32.95) were not agree with the statement. 69 (54.4%) were agree with the statement that Co-education is still disrespected in Pakhtoon society and 58 (45.6%) were not agree with the statement. 97 (76.9%) were agree with the statement that Female access to higher education is less due to transportation facilities and 30 (23.1%) were not agree with the statement. 111 (87.1%) were agree with the statement that Women harassment is a hurdle to female higher education and 16 (12.9%) were not agree with the statement. 90 (70.3%) were agree with the statement that Due to gender discrimination people just educate male members in their family. (29.7%) were not agree with the statement. 92 (72.9%) were agree with the statement that Poverty is responsible for less female access to higher education and 35 (27.15) were not agree with the statement. 109 (85.55) were agree with the statement that People think that female higher education dishonors their family. 18

(14.5%) were not agree. 107 (84.9%) were agree with the statement that Shortage of educational institutions is responsible for female no access to higher education and 20 (15.1%) were not agree with the statement. 109 (85.5%) were agree with the statement that Earlier marriages of females is also a problem in the way of female higher education and 18 (14.5%) were not agree with the statement. 78 (61.6%) were agree with the statement that Lack of boarding facility is a major problem in the way of female higher education and 49 (38.4 %) were not agree with the statement. 89 (70.55) were agree with the statement that less number of female students does not encourage rest of the female students and 38 (29.5%) were not agree with the statement. 112 (88.8%) respondents were agree with the statement that their parents favor women higher education and 15 (11.2%) were not agree with the statement. 80 (62.3%) were agree with the statement that their families prefer male higher education as compared to female higher education and 47 (37.7%) were not agree with the statement. 110 (86.3%) were agree with the statement that most of parents do not send their daughters to higher education institutions due to long distance and 17 (13.7%) were not agree with the statement. 109 (85.5%) respondents were agree with the statement that they like female higher education and 18 (14.55) were not agree with the statement. 101 (79.1%) were agree with the statement that their culture is male dominated which has a very less space for female higher education. 26 (20.9%) were not agree with the statement. 95 (74.3%) were agree with the statement that The environment inside the education institutions is conducive for female

education and 32 (25.7%) were not agree with the statement. 115 (90.4%) were agree with the statement that Separate educational institutions will encourage female higher education and 12 (9.6%) were not agree with the statement. 114 (98.6%) were agree with the statement that they face hurdles in getting higher education and 13 (10.4%) were not agree with the statement. 93 (73.7%) were agree with the statement that they encourage their relatives for female higher education in their locality and 34 (26,3%) were not agree with the statement.

CONCLUSION

This study was conducted to explore the social and cultural constraints in the way of female in getting higher education. After analyzing the data of the current study, it is concluded that majority of the respondents were the age range between 18-22 years, married, were belonging to joint family, barriers in getting higher education, co-education is disrespected in Pukhtoon society, lack of transportation facilities and women harassment is a hurdle to female higher education. Furthermore, gender discrimination, poverty, people think that female higher education dishonors their family, shortage of educational institutions, early marriages of females, lack hostel facility, preference to male higher education and long distance to educational institutions were responsible factors for low enrolment of female in higher educational institutions.

5.3 Recommendations

On the basis of the above findings of the study, this study suggests the following recommendations;

1. There is a need to create awareness in masses regarding the importance of female higher education.
2. Establishment of separate educational institutions for female higher education is needed.
3. Government should provide less expensive education and scholarships to female for getting higher education.
4. Religious scholars should talk on the importance of female education on different occasions.

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